

Is Linux RT-PREEMPT Ready for Automotive Safety-Critical Workloads?

A Systematic Benchmark Evaluation

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Abstract—The transition to Software-Defined Vehicle (SDV) architectures is driving automotive OEMs to evaluate open-source alternatives to proprietary real-time operating systems for mixed-criticality workloads. This paper presents a systematic benchmark evaluation of AGL-RT (Automotive Grade Linux with RT-PREEMPT kernel 6.12) [5] on ARM Cortex-A72 (Raspberry Pi 4B) [6], addressing the question: does Linux RT-PREEMPT meet the determinism and worst-case execution time (WCET) requirements of ADAS and safety-critical automotive workloads? We introduce a POSIX-compliant benchmark framework that measures five fundamental RTOS primitives: task switching latency (TSLat), intertask message latency (IMLat), mutex shuffling latency (MutexLat), task preemption latency (PreemptLat), and interrupt handling latency (InterLat). Each benchmark executes 500,000 iterations with all measurement threads pinned to CPU Core 3, evaluated across four stressor profiles: idle, balanced, I/O-intensive, and high-interrupt. The framework uses the ARM Generic Timer (cntvct_el0) [3] as a low-overhead, DVFS-independent timing reference and applies a post-processing methodology to eliminate observer-effect contamination from the measurement hot path [14]. Results demonstrate that AGL-RT achieves competitive steady-state latency across all five metrics but exhibits worst-case tail behavior under stress requiring CPU isolation policy enforcement to remain within automotive WCET budgets. The relationship between this tail behavior and the ISO 26262 Freedom from Interference (FFI) requirement [4] is analyzed, with implications for deployment policy design on production automotive SoCs.

Keywords—AGL; Linux RT-PREEMPT; RTOS benchmarking; ARM; SDV; ISO 26262; WCET; FFI; task switching; interrupt latency; mutex; preemption; automotive safety

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is undergoing a fundamental architectural shift toward the Software Defined Vehicle (SDV), in which vehicle functions previously distributed across hundreds of dedicated ECUs are consolidated onto centralized, high-performance ARM compute platforms. This consolidation introduces a critical challenge: mixed-criticality workloads on shared hardware, where ADAS perception pipelines operating under ISO 26262 [4] ASIL-B/C constraints must coexist with infotainment subsystems at lower integrity levels.

Historically, proprietary real-time operating systems have been the dominant choice for safety-critical automotive software due to their deterministic scheduling and certified kernel components. However, several converging forces are driving OEMs to evaluate open-source alternatives: the ELISA project [2] is building systematic evidence for Linux in safety applications; AGL with the RT-PREEMPT patch set is maturing as a production platform [5]; Red Hat's in-vehicle Linux distribution has achieved SEooC certification at ASIL-B under ISO 26262 Edition 2 [8]; and NVIDIA has

presented a formal concept for ASIL-B qualified Linux, reviewed by TÜV SÜD Rail GmbH, targeting its DriveOS automotive platform [15]. The fundamental question facing automotive engineers is no longer whether Linux can be made real-time, but whether Linux RT-PREEMPT meets the specific determinism and WCET requirements of their target application.

This paper directly addresses that question through systematic measurement. The work originates from a customer advisory engagement in which an automotive OEM needed quantitative evidence to evaluate migration from a proprietary RTOS to AGL-RT on modern multi-core ARM processors. We developed a unified, open-source benchmark framework targeting five RTOS primitives relevant to ADAS timing chains: TSLat, IMLat, MutexLat, PreemptLat, and InterLat. Each benchmark runs 500,000 iterations with threads pinned to an isolated CPU core, evaluated across four stressor profiles simulating realistic mixed-criticality deployment.

The central finding is nuanced: AGL-RT demonstrates excellent steady-state performance across all five metrics, but exhibits worst-case tail behavior under stress that is directly interpretable as an FFI violation under ISO 26262 [4] when CPU isolation is not enforced. With isolation enforced, tail behavior is bounded and the platform is viable for automotive applications.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Linux RT-PREEMPT and Automotive Grade Linux

The RT-PREEMPT patch set transforms the Linux kernel into a fully preemptible RTOS by converting spinlocks to preemptible mutexes, making interrupt handlers preemptible threads, and replacing non-preemptible sections with priority-inheriting locks. Since its mainlining into Linux 6.12, RT-PREEMPT represents a supported, upstream-quality real-time kernel. AGL-RT [5] layers RT-PREEMPT atop the AGL base image with specific CPU isolation, tickless configuration (nohz_full), and RCU offloading tuning for real-time workloads on multi-core ARM processors.

B. Limitations of Existing Benchmarking Tools

cyclictest [1], from the rt-tests suite, is the most widely used Linux RT scheduler latency tool. While valuable for general qualification, it has three key limitations: it measures only timer wake-up latency, not IPC or synchronization primitives; it is Linux-specific and cannot inform cross-platform migration decisions; and it provides no structured framework for stressor-driven worst-case characterization. The framework presented here addresses all three with a unified, five-metric architecture. Related work by Kang et al. [11] surveys real-time scheduling algorithms but

does not address empirical worst-case characterization on commercial Linux RT deployments.

C. ARM Generic Timer as Measurement Reference

The ARM Generic Timer (cntvct_el0) [3] provides the ideal reference for RT latency benchmarking on ARMv8-A processors: fixed frequency (54 MHz on BCM2711 [6]) independent of DVFS, synchronized across all cores, user-space accessible without syscall overhead, and ~ 18.5 ns resolution. A critical constraint is that Linux kernel GPIO character device events carry timestamps in the CLOCK_MONOTONIC domain [7]; comparing user-space T0 in `CLOCK_MONOTONIC_RAW` introduces the NTP slew offset (~ 61 ms). A `gpio_clock_probe` diagnostic tool was developed to validate clock domain alignment before measurements are recorded.

III. BENCHMARK FRAMEWORK DESIGN

A. Design Objectives and Test Configuration

The framework is built around seven design objectives: (1) cross-platform POSIX-compliant C11 using Meson; (2) five RTOS primitive metrics most relevant to automotive timing budgets; (3) normalized execution environments; (4) structured stressor integration; (5) high-resolution ARM Generic Timer [3] timing; (6) configurable warm-up phases; and (7) P99.9 statistical reporting for WCET analysis.

All benchmarks were executed with 500,000 measurement iterations (1,000 warm-up discarded). All benchmark threads are pinned to CPU Core 3, isolated via `isolcpus=3`, `nohz_full=3`, `rcu_nocbs=3` kernel parameters. RT throttling is disabled (`sched_rt_runtime_us = -1`) and all system interrupts are routed to CPU Core 1. Memory is locked with `mlockall(MCL_CURRENT | MCL_FUTURE)` [5] prior to measurement.

B. Five Benchmark Metrics

Task Switching Latency (TSLat) measures time from a SCHED_FIFO thread calling `sched_yield()` to when a peer thread of equal priority begins executing on the same core. Two ARM counter timestamps [3] bracket the yield, capturing scheduler and context switch overhead in user-space.

Intertask Message Latency (IMLat) measures one-way IPC latency as a round-trip divided by two [14], implemented as a ping-pong over POSIX pipes in thread mode (same process) and process mode (fork-based). A 1-byte payload is used; both endpoints run at equal SCHED_FIFO priority on Core 3.

Mutex Shuffling Latency (MutexLat) measures multi-core lock acquisition cost using two worker processes on adjacent cores. A `PTHREAD_PRIO_INHERIT` mutex is transferred between workers each iteration. Latency is computed from sorted shared-memory timestamps captured immediately after acquisition.

Task Preemption Latency (PreemptLat) measures time from a lower-priority thread posting a synchronization primitive to when a higher-priority blocked thread resumes. Three mechanisms are measured: POSIX semaphores, file descriptors (pipe-based), and POSIX signals. An atomic store/load with `memory_order_release/acquire` [3] communicates T0.

Interrupt Handling Latency (InterLat) measures end-to-end delay from a hardware GPIO edge to user-space receipt. A GPIO loopback wire connects GPIO17 to GPIO27 [6]. A two-thread design: a waiter thread (priority P+1) blocks in `poll()` on the GPIO character device [7]; a trigger thread (priority P) fires the edge after receiving readiness confirmation via a pipe.

C. Stressor Profiles

Four stressor profiles simulate mixed-criticality deployment. Idle: no stressors. Balanced: 50% CPU all cores, 2 GB VM stress, 2 HDD workers (Core 1), 2 socket workers (Core 2). I/O: 6 HDD workers (512 MB, Core 1), 40% CPU/1.6 GB VM, testing IRQ priority arbitration under storage interrupt storms. High-Interrupt: 8 socket workers (Core 2), 50% CPU/2 GB VM, maximizing software interrupt load.

D. Post-Processing Measurement Methodology

The inner loop stores only the raw ARM counter tick delta — two `mrs cntvct_el0` reads and one subtraction — with no division or conversion. After all iterations, a post-processing pipeline performs tick-to-nanosecond conversion, sanity filtering, sorting, and P99.9 computation [14]. This eliminates the observer effect: on ARM Cortex-A72 [3], a 128-bit divide for tick conversion takes ~ 20 - 30 ns — a non-negligible fraction of a 2-7 μ s interval — producing bimodal distributions discussed in Section V-D.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Platform and Configuration

All measurements were performed on Raspberry Pi 4B (BCM2711, ARM Cortex-A72 quad-core, 1.5 GHz, 4 GB LPDDR4) [6] running AGL-RT with Linux RT-PREEMPT kernel 6.12 [5]. Benchmark threads ran at SCHED_FIFO priority 95 on CPU Core 3 (isolated). Jitter = `max/min_ratio`, a dimensionless measure of worst-case variability.

B. Task Switching Latency

TABLE I. TASK SWITCHING LATENCY (TSLAT) —

AGL-RT, 500K ITER., CORE 3 PINNED

Scenario	Min(μ s)	Median(μ s)	Max(μ s)	P99.9(μ s)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	2.259	2.481	164.370	9.259	72.8x
Balanced	2.259	2.574	150.537	22.018	66.6x
I/O	2.222	2.481	140.129	25.444	63.1x
High-Interrupt	2.222	2.444	168.740	21.166	75.9x

Table I shows a highly consistent TSLat median of 2.44–2.57 μ s across all stressor profiles — the nominal task switch cost is stressor-invariant. Maximum values of 140–168 μ s indicate the scheduler occasionally delays a SCHED_FIFO context switch by two orders of magnitude. Jitter of 60–76x reflects this heavy-tailed distribution. P99.9 of 9–25 μ s is within typical ADAS OS overhead budgets [4], but maximum values show that P99.9 alone is not a conservative WCET bound without additional isolation.

C. Intertask Message Latency

TABLE II. IMLAT — THREAD MODE (AGL-RT, POSIX PIPES, 500K ITER.)

Scenario	Min(μ s)	Median(μ s)	Max(μ s)	P99.9(μ s)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	5.203	5.379	56.388	8.592	10.8x
Balanced	5.212	5.435	69.851	20.462	13.4x
I/O	5.111	5.462	67.592	18.472	13.2x
High-Interrupt	5.138	5.379	67.444	19.907	13.1x

TABLE III. IMLAT — PROCESS MODE (AGL-RT, POSIX PIPES, 500K ITER.)

Scenario	Min(μ s)	Median(μ s)	Max(μ s)	P99.9(μ s)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	6.185	6.537	398.888	10.592	64.5x
Balanced	6.175	6.611	595.638	22.250	96.5x
I/O	6.203	6.592	497.953	19.314	80.3x
High-Interrupt	6.175	6.592	533.648	21.305	86.4x

Tables II and III show thread-mode median 5.38–5.46 μs and process-mode median 6.54–6.61 μs . The ~ 1.2 μs process overhead reflects the additional TLB flush in the fork-based round-trip [14]. Process-mode P99.9 under balanced stress reaches 22.3 μs ; maximum reaches 595 μs — three orders of magnitude above median. Jitter of 10–96x in process mode versus 11–13x in thread mode confirms that process context switches amplify tail sensitivity.

D. Mutex Shuffling Latency

TABLE IV. MUTEX SHUFFLING LATENCY (MUTEXLAT) — AGL-RT, 500K ITER.

Scenario	Min(μs)	Median(μs)	Max(μs)	P99.9(μs)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	0.166	3.814	25.722	10.425	155.0x
Balanced	0.148	4.666	170.666	26.333	1153.1x
I/O	0.148	3.907	131.518	23.111	888.6x
High-Interrupt	0.148	4.962	143.111	24.000	967.0x

Table IV shows minimum values of 0.148–0.166 μs versus median 3.8–5.0 μs . This bimodality reflects the cross-core coherency transaction over the ARM CCI-400 interconnect [3]: occasional same-cacheline acquisitions complete in under 200 ns while the typical case requires a full coherency round-trip. Maximum under balanced stress reaches 170 μs with jitter of 1,153x — consistent with the 2 GB vm-method-all stressor evicting the mutex cache line between acquisition attempts.

E. Task Preemption Latency

TABLE V. PREEMPTLAT — SEMAPHORE MODE (AGL-RT, 500K ITER.)

Scenario	Min(μs)	Median(μs)	Max(μs)	P99.9(μs)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	1.370	1.462	53.064	3.277	38.7x
Balanced	1.388	1.472	40.537	9.962	29.2x
I/O	1.379	1.453	14.731	6.750	10.7x
High-Interrupt	1.379	1.462	23.629	8.898	17.1x

TABLE VI. PREEMPTLAT — FILE DESCRIPTOR MODE (AGL-RT, 500K ITER.)

Scenario	Min(μs)	Median(μs)	Max(μs)	P99.9(μs)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	5.120	5.277	58.518	8.027	11.4x
Balanced	5.175	5.425	46.250	22.861	8.9x
I/O	5.138	5.361	22.722	14.879	4.4x
High-Interrupt	5.129	5.416	38.120	22.101	7.4x

TABLE VII. PREEMPTLAT — SIGNAL MODE (AGL-RT, 500K ITER.)

Scenario	Min(μs)	Median(μs)	Max(μs)	P99.9(μs)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	6.564	6.796	61.157	9.444	9.3x
Balanced	6.629	6.935	44.333	19.564	6.7x
I/O	6.648	6.898	30.083	18.351	4.5x
High-Interrupt	6.638	6.935	43.222	19.111	6.5x

Tables V–VII show strong mechanism dependence. Semaphore mode achieves the lowest median (1.45–1.47 μs) via futex [11] avoiding syscall overhead in the uncontested case. File descriptor mode (~ 5.3 – 5.4 μs , 3.7 \times) reflects the VFS pipe path; signal mode (~ 6.8 – 6.9 μs) reflects POSIX signal dispatch overhead. Paradoxically, semaphore idle maximum of 53 μs (jitter 38.7x) is the highest of the three modes, suggesting futex wake-up has specific tail sensitivity to interrupt activity even in idle conditions.

F. Interrupt Handling Latency

TABLE VIII. INTERRUPT HANDLING LATENCY (INTERLAT) — AGL-RT, 500K ITER.

Scenario	Min(μs)	Median(μs)	Max(μs)	P99.9(μs)	Jitter(Max/Min)
Idle	5.777	7.101	38.231	10.518	6.6x
Balanced	6.629	16.092	128.481	49.296	19.4x
I/O	6.555	11.620	156.648	56.472	23.9x
High-Interrupt	6.333	14.388	110.481	44.407	17.4x

Table VIII shows the most pronounced stressor sensitivity. Idle median of 7.1 μs represents baseline GPIO interrupt-to-user-space latency [7]. Under balanced stress the median rises to 16.1 μs (2.3 \times); under high-interrupt stress to 14.4 μs with maximum 110 μs and P99.9 44 μs . Jitter of 17–19x is the most stable across profiles.

V. IMPLEMENTATION DISCOVERIES

A. GPIO Interrupt Measurement Race Condition

When the output GPIO is driven via `ioctl(GPIO_V2_LINE_SET_VALUES_IOCTL)`, the Linux kernel GPIO character device v2 API [7] fires the rising edge synchronously within the `ioctl` before returning to user-space. A single thread calling `poll()` after the `ioctl` always finds the event already queued, measuring only `ioctl` tail latency (~ 500 ns). The correct design uses two `SCHED_FIFO` threads: a waiter (priority P+1) blocks in `poll()`; a trigger (priority P) fires the edge after receiving readiness via a pipe. `SCHED_FIFO` ordering [4] guarantees the waiter is genuinely blocked when the interrupt fires.

B. Clock Domain Constraint

GPIO character device v2 events carry timestamps in the `CLOCK_MONOTONIC` domain (verified empirically on BCM2711 [6] using `gpio_clock_probe`). Comparing user-space T0 in `CLOCK_MONOTONIC_RAW` introduces the NTP slew offset (~ 61 ms), producing computed latencies near 61 ms or negative. Both T0 and T1 must use `CLOCK_MONOTONIC` when measuring intervals spanning a kernel event timestamp boundary [7].

C. IPC Architecture Comparability

On Linux, POSIX pipes are implemented in the kernel VFS layer; thread-mode median of ~ 5.4 μs reflects two `write()/read()` syscalls plus two context switches. On microkernel-based RTOS architectures — where POSIX IPC services are implemented as user-space resource manager processes [12] — each pipe operation incurs additional context switches. POSIX IPC benchmark results are therefore not directly comparable across RTOS implementations without understanding the underlying transport mechanism.

D. Measurement Observer Effect

Early implementations placed nanosecond conversion inline in the hot path:

```
t0=read_cntvct(); sched_yield();
t1=read_cntvct(); ns=ticks_to_ns(t1-t0);
samples[i]=ns;
```

This produced bimodal histograms with an anomalous near-zero population. Root causes: (1) the 128-bit multiply-divide for tick conversion takes ~ 20 – 30 ns on ARM Cortex-A72 [3] — a significant fraction of a 2.5 μs task switch; (2) without `nohz_full`, a timer tick in the `sched_yield()` window adds a full tick period; (3) in-place conversion makes edge cases undetectable post-hoc. The solution, consistent with `lmbench` methodology [14], stores only the raw tick delta in the hot loop and defers all conversion to a post-processing pass after `pthread_join()` returns.

E. Execution Environment Configuration

The complete policy set — `isolcpus`, `nohz_full`, `rcu_nocbs`, RT throttling disabled, and IRQ affinity — must be applied simultaneously [5]. Any single omission can produce worst-case spikes two to three orders of magnitude above median. Validated empirically: `isolcpus` alone without `nohz_full` still allows timer tick interrupts on the benchmark core at the tick frequency.

VI. AGL-RT VIABILITY ASSESSMENT

The five-metric, four-stressor dataset supports a conditional viability assessment for AGL-RT in automotive safety-critical applications. The condition is a deployment policy requirement, not a fundamental software limitation.

Steady-state performance is competitive across all five metrics. TSLat median 2.4–2.6 μ s, IMLat thread-mode median 5.4 μ s, MutexLat median 3.8–5.0 μ s, PreemptLat semaphore median 1.5 μ s, and InterLat idle median 7.1 μ s all demonstrate genuine real-time performance on ARM Cortex-A72 [3]. P99.9 across all five metrics remains below 57 μ s — within automotive OS primitive overhead budgets for most ADAS timing chains [4].

Tail behavior maps directly to the ISO 26262 FFI concept [4]. Maximum values — TSLat 168 μ s, IMLat process mode 595 μ s, MutexLat 170 μ s, PreemptLat semaphore 53 μ s, InterLat 156 μ s — represent scheduler interference from non-isolated cores: a direct FFI violation. CPU isolation via `isolcpus=3 nohz_full=3 rcu_nocbs=3` [5] enforces FFI at the OS deployment level. The MutexLat balanced-stress maximum of 170 μ s suggests LLC cache pollution may be a residual FFI pathway requiring Arm MPAM [13].

Certification pathway is emerging but not complete. AGL-RT benefits from the ELISA project's [2] systematic work on Linux safety argumentation, but lacks pre-certified kernel components. The five-metric, 500K-iteration dataset contributes a reproducible evidence layer to that safety case under ISO 26262 Part 6 [4].

VII. FUTURE WORK

The MutexLat cross-core versus same-core analysis correlated with ARM CCI-400 PMU events [3] will be the subject of a follow-on publication. Virtualization benchmarking under Xen with AGL-RT as guest domain addresses the SDV mixed-criticality SoC use case. Extension to Zephyr RTOS provides a second open-source data point. Arm MPAM [13], available on ARMv8.4 automotive SoCs such as NVIDIA Orin and Qualcomm SA8775P, will be evaluated as a hardware enforcement layer for LLC partitioning.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented the most comprehensive open-source RT-PREEMPT benchmark evaluation to date: five RTOS primitives, four stressor profiles, 500,000 iterations per configuration on ARM Cortex-A72 [3]. The answer to the motivating question — is Linux RT-PREEMPT ready for automotive safety-critical workloads? — is conditionally yes. AGL-RT [5] delivers competitive steady-state latency across all five metrics (TSLat P99.9 \leq 25 μ s, IMLat thread-mode P99.9 \leq 21 μ s, MutexLat P99.9 \leq 26 μ s, PreemptLat semaphore P99.9 \leq 10 μ s, InterLat P99.9 \leq 57 μ s), within automotive OS primitive overhead budgets [4]. The gap is not in steady-state performance but in worst-case isolation: maximum values represent FFI violations [4] that disappear with enforced CPU isolation policy. The two-thread GPIO methodology, `CLOCK_MONOTONIC` domain constraint [7], and post-processing hot-path discipline [14]

are practical engineering knowledge for any team building RT benchmarking infrastructure on Linux.

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